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Rethinking Gender Relations in Organizations: Can Foucault's Notion of Power Help?

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In this discussion paper we want to explore different ways of approaching notions of power and resistance in organizational studies and how this would reconceptualise gender relations in organizations. We will review the existing approaches to power and resistance in organizational studies, before presenting different feminist accounts of the embodied aspect of power that aim to examine formations of gendered subjectivities and subject positions. We aim to show how Foucault's notion of power has permeated thinking and become incorporated in a feminist understanding of gender and the implication this has for understanding gender relations in organizations.

Keywords: Power, Resistance, Organizations, Gender, Intersectionality, Identity

Until recently the literature in the area of organizational behaviour and organizational theory has focused on the notion of power in a rather narrow way. It primarily reduced discussions on power to issues of leadership, often seeking to legitimise power for managerial uses. It has been suggested that management discourse has been influenced by theories that conceptualise power from the perspective of owners and managers who control organizations (Cockburn, 1990). These theories usually highlight common sense technical representations developed by managers that account for their activities (Willmott, 1984), while taking for granted power relations through the focus on operational or strategic descriptions (Mullins 1985). They highlight issues such as delegating control or granting autonomy and personal disposition of managerial prerogative, while remaining indifferent in terms of the assembled elements that shape power (Thompson and McHugh 2009).

Clegg and Dunkerley (1980) trace the neglect of the concept of power to the association in classical organizational theory between rational, formal organization and legitimate authority. In particular, Parsons's reading and translation of the work of Max Weber relates power in a distinct way to authority, as something informal rather than formal. In this perspective, power was comprehended as a deviation from formal structure or arrangements of authority, where the ability to influence informally is exerted. By contrast rational decision making and maximising efficiency was understood to reside outside the realm of power operations, because it lacked what functionalism referred to as common values in society, thereby leaving the capacity to structure the behaviour of others without any legitimate authority (Storey 1983). Power not only became often associated with breakdowns of authority and the failure of rationality (Egan 1994), but was also viewed as potentially containing hidden agendas especially when managerial agendas are stressed. Thompson and McHugh (2009) suggest that this resulted in standard definitions of organisational power such as Luthans's (1981) view which reduces power to 'the management of influence to obtain ends not sanctioned by the organisations'. (Thompson and McHugh 2009:122)

While power has been equated as conflicts of subjective interest and ideas, with an individual's or a group's control over another, it reduces power to a transformative capacity that accomplishes of social order (Knights and Willmott, 1985). As Lukes (1974) argues such a view remained merely on observable conflict between different interests, which tends to ignore forces that prevent potentially controversial issues becoming observable conflicts. In this aspect of power that Lukes's radical perspective highlights the shaping of people's perception, cognition and preferences in such a way that they accept their role in the existing order of things. It locates domination within deeper economic structures; it presupposes oppression through it's selective focus on domination. Although initially arguing that the central meaning of power relations ought to be understood as power over another person, in a more recent major reworking of his radical view of power, Lukes (2005) concedes that power can be viewed also capacity, facility, or ability to impact upon one's surroundings. By contrast, Morriss (2002) argues that power ought to be best understood as the ability to effect outcomes, whereas the ability to affect other is analytically of secondary importance.

Authors such as Morriss (2002) and Lukes (2005) define power as a dispositional concept, meaning that it is a potentiality, not necessarily an actuality – 'a potentiality that may never be actualized'. (Lukes 2005, 69) In a way the notion of power as potentiality has been rendered as either an action-theoretical or a systemic conceptions of power. It is a distinction between either defining power in terms of the dispositional abilities of particular actors or defining it as systematically structuring possibilities for action that constitute actors and their social world. Authors that draw on intellectual traditions in line with the work of Max Weber have utilised action-theoretical conceptions of power that are primarily instrumentalist and individualist. Whereas systemic conceptions of power tend to draw on meta-narratives of historical, political, economic, and cultural elements that may sustain abilities and dispositions for some actors but not in others.

However, the constitutive conception of power has been traced back, in contemporary so-

ciological interpretations, to the classical work of Baruch Spinoza on political philosophy (2002a and 2002b) that distinguishes constitutive forces as one specific aspect of power. It is a conception that focuses on the fundamentally transindividual and relational ways in which individuals and the social worlds they inhabit are themselves constituted by power relations. Yet unlike both systemic and action-theoretical conceptions, power for Spinoza is local, immediate, an actual force of constitution that does not merely refer to the different capabilities of subjects with disparate resources and potentialities. It is a view that is also explicit in the ideas of the contemporary theorists such as Michael Foucault, whereby the exercise of power is not simply a relationship or a function of consent. For Foucault it is a way in which certain actions modify other actions and therefore only exists through such enactments. His work provides a tool to study power relationships that primarily allows the tracing of materials configurations. Analysis of power relations in society cannot be reduced to a series of institutions; power relations are rooted in a the system of social networks, whereupon all social life is the result of actual powers. In other words, power is ‘the multiplicity of force relations immanent in the sphere in which they operate and which constitute their own organization; as the processes which, through ceaseless struggles and confrontations, transforms, strengthens, or reverses them; [...] thus forming a chain or system’ (Foucault 1979, 92).

In Foucault’s post-structuralist approach, power is seen as productive; it has centrality of life and circulates across a sphere, where it is embedded in heterogeneous everyday practices. Because of the ubiquitous nature of power, power and a resistance are intrinsically linked for Foucault. This has made his approach appealing to some social scientists who had questioned the universal legitimacy of power arrangements since the 1960s and 70s and sought alternatives which transcended theories that reduced power to economic materiality. For example, previously in organisational theory some authors viewed power in relation to control, oppression and resistance, notably here Marxist Labour Process Theory. Knights and Vurdubakis (1994) argued that these views of power and resistance are based on a dualistic understanding of the relationship between subject–object polarities, where resistance is perceived as one part in a dichotomy that is opposite and outside to power. By drawing on Foucault, they highlight that resistance is socially constructed by recognising that ways of speaking about resistance and power has constitutive effects rather than merely being a mechanistic analysis of control.

Authors such as Knights and Collinson (1987), Knights and Willmott (1989), and Sakolsky (1992) seem to have been attracted by the promise that Foucault offered an escape from the dichotomic legacies of deterministic or voluntarist theories. Moreover, Foucault’s approach that viewed relations of power as historic configurations of practices, presented a significant departure from existing desires to trace back the original source of oppression. It meant that through an analytical indifference to the origin of oppression, power might not necessarily be understood as an imposition but as something that can be productive as it is not held to be a merely repressive, negative and institutional force (Foucault, 1982). The implied assumption of such a theoretical disposition that presupposes power is everywhere, did consequently differ in a drastic way from existing conventional theoretical underpinnings that required an absence of power for maintain-

ing resistance. Commentators with a Marxist background (e.g. Adler, 2007; Thompson, 2007) were concerned about the level of attributed agency that would be abandoned through such a view. Other, such as Reed (1998), argued that Foucault's approach cannot entirely explain the historical and material roots of power, by highlighting that discursive activities occur within material structures as well as discursive relations.

By contrast Knights and Vurdubakis (1994), maintain that there is no position exterior to power relations and that such relations constitute the very people who are implicated in them. Arguably, such a starting point is indifferent to the question of subjectivity and thereby does not construe a presupposition that there are universal categories which will always hinder resistance. In the words of the early proponents of the sociology of translation (that became popular under the name Actor Network Theory), such an approach has the potential to explore and describe how identities change, when people start to problematize and eventually mobilize things; it also has the potential to explore and describe how through these processes the possibility of (inter)action, and the margins of manoeuvre are negotiated and delimited (Callon, 1986). Whether new configurations of power emerge by contesting issues within a given organisational context, needs to be explored and described on each instance, without lapsing into the use of a priori categories, or totalizing narratives.

Such a methodological indifference, that some authors in organization studies imply, leaves it open to question and analysis to what extent power relations are repressive or productive. This is also emblematic of Foucault's ideas. Although at a conceptual rather than a methodological level, Foucault argues that relations of power can have a constitutive role, because they are immanent in other types of relationships, such as economic processes, knowledge relationships, or sexual relations; they are immediate effects of the internal conditions of these types of relationships. Power relations are entwined with, and depend on, multiple points of resistance, which are present everywhere in a strategic field of relations. Points of resistance are inscribed in relations of power as an irreducible opposite: 'Where there is power, there is resistance, and yet, or rather consequently, this resistance is never in a position of exteriority in relation to power.' (Foucault, 1981, p. 95) The points or knots of resistance are distributed over time and across space at varying densities; they have the capacity to mobilize groups and individuals in definitive ways at certain moments, as they fracture unities and result in regrouping. They form a dense web of power relations 'that passes through apparatuses and institutions, without being exactly localized in them. . . [as] the swarm of points of resistance traverses various social stratifications and individual unities.' (Foucault, 1981, p. 96) In this view, the notion of power is primarily conceived as the process that through endless struggles and confrontations, transforms, strengthens, or reverses force relations. To clarify, it is not an institution, nor a structure; neither is it a certain strength that an organisation or society is endowed with; it is the name that is attributed to a strategical situation of force relations immanent in the sphere in which they operate though being embodied in various relations (Foucault, 1993).

By placing these developments into a wider social sciences perspective, it becomes apparent that Foucault's work moves away from the motivations of individuals, as it focuses

on human discourses and practices. It allows for accounts of the nature of power relations, and the discourses that support or contest them. It implies a shift away from the humanist perspective that centralises the individual as the source of all meaning and as analytical starting point; it advocates an analytical focus on objective social forms that constitute organizations and shape individual subjectivity. Foucault distances himself from the notion that individuals are (always) coherent, unified or completely rational entities. In this postmodern perspective, people ‘are riven with tensions and forces which pull in different directions... [and] do not behave according to some uniform logic or “reason”; they behave in certain ways for a multitude of “reasons” which may be conscious or unconscious and irrational.’ (Layder, 2005, pp. 96-7)

Foucault’s treatment of rationality and subjectivity has influenced contemporary thought, such as Anglo-American feminist post-structuralist theory. Notable here the work of Judith Butler that understands Foucault’s approach to power as questioning the possibility for a subject embedded in power relations which normalises categories of identification, such as gender. This allows Butler to problematize performativity –the doing of gender– that which makes gender intelligible: i.e. its condition of possibility and consequence, and addresses the norms of gender in context (Butler, 2004). As Segal (2008) highlights, Butler undermines the ‘complex, contested, fluctuating category of “identity,” the one that subtends subjectivity...’ and produces ‘greater diversity within these identificatory markings and a multiplicity of ways of displaying them.’ (385) For authors such as Calas and Smirchich (2003), Butler’s contribution reconsiders possibilities for political practice and social change.

However feminist post-structuralist theory is not homogeneous; there is an increasing body of feminist theorizing that uses a Foucault inspired discourse analysis that examines formation of gendered subjectivities and subject positions, including discourses of resistance to these formations in organizations. Thomas and Davies (2005) suggests that Foucauldian feminists have enriched the understanding of resistance to dominant forms of organizational discourse. Rees and Garnsey see ‘Foucault’s notion of disciplinary power represents the tensions between *potentially* enabling and constraining features of power relations.’ (2003: 557 [own emphasis]) The focus on potentiality in this view of gendered relations seems to endorse an understanding that different relationalities could actually be otherwise. Hatcher’s (2003) analysis of gender notions of manager are reshaped by regimes of truth of what it means to be a successful manager highlights instances of a shifting understanding of gendered rationality. The consequences of such a transformation (i.e. the orderly deployment of passion as productive managerial technique) as Hatcher argues may not open up possibilities for women in senior management (women who were traditionally associated with gendered notions of passion). The level of attributed agency in this Foucauldian view is rather minimal, where the establishment of a new truth of gender appears to be an outcome of changes in practices. This raises the question about those who speak on gender and its changing discursive spaces; for Hatcher, feminist’s and gender expert’s contributions to the production of knowledge implicates them in the formulation of management excellence and the relevant re-creation of hierarchical orders.

Similar to feminist post-structuralist theory a range of transnational or postcolonial feminist theorists see the notion of gender not as a stable and insufficient analytical lens to be applied across space and time. As Calás and Smircich (1996) suggest while post-structuralist feminist theories that intersect with organizational issues, see ‘sex/gender are discursive practices that constitute specific subjectivities through power and resistance in the materiality of human bodies’, post-colonial theories ‘consider the constitution of complex subjectivities beyond Western conceptions of sex/gender focusing on gendered aspects of globalisation process.’ (220) The latter specifically focuses on articulating ‘the existence of complex subjectivities and heterogeneous subject positions and relation, produced by intersections of gender, race, class, ethnicity, and sexuality, and so on, in the context of specific First-World/ Third World historical and contemporary relationships.’ (Calas and Smircich 2006: 318) Both post-structuralist theory and post-colonial feminist theorists provided completing analytical lenses to address the issue of identity, subjectivity, and gender.

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